

High-Spin Cobalt (II) Heterochelates*

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In an extension of our previous work on the synthesis, characterisation and rate measurements on transition metal heterochelates¹⁻⁶, this communication reports the synthesis of some cobalt(II) heterochelates containing acetoacetarylamide and orthophenanthroline/2-2'-dipyridyl.

For the synthesis of the heterochelates the wellknown method of replacement of unidentate ligands by a chelating ligand in complexes of the type $[M(AA) X_2]^{+n}$ (where AA=bidentate ligand, X=unidentate ligand) was chosen⁵. We have in our hands⁴ the dipyridine bis (acetoacet-o-toluidido) cobalt(II), dipyridine bis (acetoacet o-chloroanilido) cobalt(II) to effect such synthesis. The two pyridines in these complexes were replaced by strongly chelating ligand orthophenanthroline or 2-2'-dipyridyl with the formation of heterogeneous inner shell around cobalt(II).

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetoacet-o-toluidide, acetoacet o-chloroanilide, orthophenanthroline and 2-2'-dipyridyl were B.D.H. (England) L.R. variety and used without further purification. All other chemicals used were of E. Merck's G. R. variety.

Dipyridine bis (acetoacet-o-toluidido) cobalt(II) and dipyridine bis (acetoacet-o-chloroanilido) cobalt(II) were prepared according to the method described earlier.⁴

General method of synthesis of cobalt (II) heterochelates:—Dipyridine bis (acetoacetarylamido) cobalt (II) (0.004 mole) was dissolved in minimum amount of rectified spirit. Orthophenanthroline/2-2'-dipyridyl (0.004 mole) was dissolved in spirit (5 ml.). These two solutions were then mixed and allowed to stand for one hour with occasional stirring. The separated orange yellow crystals were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol and dried in air. The complexes are insoluble in water, soluble in methanol and ethanol.

These complexes may also be prepared starting from the corresponding β -picoline or γ -picoline complexes⁴.

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TABLE I

Cobalt(II) Heterochelates

Compound	Colour	Analytical data			Molar conductivity mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹	Magnetic moment B.M. Temp= 296°K	
		% Co	%N	%H ₂ O*			
1. [Co (ophen)(Acet-o-tol) ₂]. H ₂ O	Orange yellow	Found:	9.4	8.9	3.0	14	4.95
		Reqd:	9.2	8.7	2.8		
2. [Co (dipy) (Acet-o-tol) ₂]	Orange yellow	Found:	10.0	9.6	—	16	4.98
		Reqd:	9.9	9.4			
3. [Co(ophen)(Acet-Cl-anil) ₂]. H ₂ O	Orange yellow	Found:	8.9	8.4	3.0	15	4.96
		Reqd:	8.7	8.2	2.6		
4. [Co (dipy) (Acet-Cl-anil) ₂]	Orange yellow	Found:	9.3	9.0	—	12	4.99
		Reqd:	9.2	8.8			

where Acet-o-tol=acetoacet-o-toluidide; Acet-Cl-anil=acetoacet-orthochloroanilide; ophen=orthophenanthroline and dipy=2-2'-dipyridyl.

*by loss at 110°.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On treating dipyrindine bis (acetoacetarylamo) cobalt (II) in ethanol solution with orthophenanthroline/2-2'-dipyridyl at room temperature, there occurred evolution of pyridine and the bidentate chelating ligand slipped into the coordination zone, resulting in the formation of orange yellow low symmetry cobalt (II) complexes. The heterochelates are quite stable and do not decompose or get oxidised on heating at 120° for hours. The electrolytic conductance measurements in methanol indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The measured magnetic moments of the complexes are invariably around 4.9 B.M., which value clearly agrees with the high-spin octahedral structure, the ground level being $4T_{1g}(F)$ with $t_{2g}^5 e_g^2$ configuration⁷ In methanol solution the complexes do not show any band in the region studied (10,000-28,570 cm^{-1}), however, the molar extinction coefficients of these complexes are low (ϵ 50) in comparison to other tetrahedral cobalt (II) complexes⁸.

The instantaneous expulsion of two pyridines in dipyrindine bis(acetoacet o-toluidide) Co (II) dipyrindine bis (acetoacet o-chloroanilido) Co (II) by orthophenanthroline or 2-2'-dipyridyl at ordinary temperature points to a *cis* configuration of dipyrindine complexes. If these dipyrindine complexes belong to the *trans* category, the expulsion of unidentate ligands should have taken place at a higher temperature in order to initiate *trans-cis* isomerisation. Recently this type of chemical evidence along with others has been utilised in our Laboratory for characterisation of *cis-trans* isomers of few Co (III) complexes⁹. It may be mentioned that although conductance electronic spectra have

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been claimed to distinguish *cis-trans* isomers of Co (III) complexes of the type $(Co^{III} A_4 B_2)$ (ref. 7), these studies are of little help in characterising geometrical isomers of Co (II) complexes of the type $(Co^{II} A_4 B_2)$.

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